

A Perspective on Gravity

Navneet Bhurani

Gravity, that pulls everything? Or keeps it all in place
Intact in tact through meanings of mass that exists

Gravity is said to be all but no force at its centre,
What is gravity

Gravity is not meant to get stronger as you get closer ? But is a self sustaining way of keeping everything intact through fusion and environments that can handle or evolve to handle such conditions, are what differs us from stars ?

But at the end and in the beginning and inside we are the same ?

Taking steps back looking at it from reverse a different perspective an angle

Bombs of fire were looked from reverse
But looking at gravity to be created from reverse is the wrong way ?

Speed time distance

Everything relates everything comes together to give meaning of something greater
Even if as humans we can only perceive so little

Examples of hydron collider of 27kms becomes 7m in perception

Is it us as humans or the atom inside

What is the right perspective. Is there a right perspective is it an illusion or does it all comes together to make reason and sense of something greater

What is gravity what is a black hole

Is it a star so immense and big that collapses it masses to high perceptions

Or is it a smaller star that is capable of handling its own collapse through its environment

There is gravity in stars and planets the same way

Yet it's need to be a star so big that can't handle its own mass after its fuel ?

So is gravity inside our planets, stars, earth

A force that's pulling us from somewhere inside that wants to pull information/mass to a singular point

Or is gravity something that is at peace inside with just a reason to keep information/mass intact

Or is it both, but it can't be both.

Mass is related to gravity (gravitational pull) and so the big stars with more mass collapsing, is it to a place that wants to stay intact

Or to place which is pulling to a singularity

Yet we know all planets and stars at the same

We know black hole can exist at size of an atom and gravity is what ? How big, Is it peace is it singularity

Why is not the same. Is it the same.

Speed time distance everything increases yet it perceptions decreases

If gravity is a place of with harmony of putting and pulling and pushing mass/information together around in a such a way to create its own environment

And is the same in planets and stars

And we can try to assume that when a star so big runs of out of fuel and collapses is not the reason an infinite singularity at its centre of it's formation ?

And that with its given speeds time and distances capable of bending to the perceptions our eyes and space itself

Is the outter acting form of distance being curled shortened to an illusion? And is infact much much greater in reality.

That the distance is an illusion to our perception is infact much bigger including all the space for mass to exist without it being continually crushed.

And to show us that the mass/information that makes it to the point of event horizon where light can not escape and we can not see where and what is

Is not being crushed eternally to a point of no return but is stored in a way to be kept intact and at harmony and synchronised with everything inside

Which can help us understand better to why space and time is looked to be bent or is bent in reality with space

Weather it's an illusion or reality

Through our perception it shall look bending of space time and becomes our reality

What happens to a black hole with all the information of universe stored inside when it evaporates

The mass/information is escaped not lost, through means of black hole losing mass

What remains after everything?

Is it a singularity?

Is it gravity.

Is it as big as a city a person or atom is it smaller

Is it a source

Or is it simply a point. A single point of attraction? Is that even the right way to explain or call it

What would remain if there were to happen to more or all possible black holes ?

Points apexes nodes X

Theories of gravity being formed by way we perceive gasses to combine have not been successful? Is the way we are looking at it wrong ?

Do gasses combining in space always form a celestial body creating its own gravity its own point from its mixing

Or is it the gasses are pulled these X points of gravity and are formed together there with its harmony and synchronisation of keeping everything intact in tact

Are we formed from a black hole evaporating or are we inside a black hole

Does the evaporation of a bigger black hole solve to be everything we are

Or is it a black hole that's increasing in distance more

And how the distance is either an illusion or increases or both when nearing and entering a black hole

1. Gravity which exists only at X points the beginning source point for every celestial body which keeps things intact in perfect symmetry
2. Gravity through stages of its life , when exposed is the formation of a Black Hole
3. Black holes due to high speed can also affect distance and create an illusion of it shrinking.
4. Distance increases from nearing to entering a black hole
5. Within a Black Hole is not a singularity but a perfect symmetry
6. When traveling near the speed of light, distance is not shrinking in reality

- Can the distance increasing be increased continually or does it have an end. And if continual does it always result in a black hole to the start. What does it represent

- Planets stars everything have an X point

- Can X points be points of source of gravity

Moons must also be at X points

Million X points everywhere, It exists everywhere in symmetry but we can not perceive them yet

Does the distance keep increasing even once inside a black hole
To a point of a centre which then increases and continues

If it increases continually is there always a black hole in the centre ?
Reasoning to an infinite cycle